

H2020-FNR-2020-2 Project no. 101000560

Rapid discovery and development of enzymes for novel and greener consumer products

Research and Innovation Action (RIA)

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Duration: 4 years

D2.7 - Workflow for deep mutational scanning for ≥ 3 to 5 enzymes (public summary)

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Lead Beneficiary:	UNEXE
Other participants:	
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Microplastic and microfiber pollution has been reported in almost all earth environments and is one of the most common microparticle pollutants along shorelines. Pollution caused by washing of synthetic textiles is the main cause for microplastic pollution in the oceans and fibres contribute up to 90% total plastic mass in wastewater treatment plants. Whole organisms have been shown to degrade microplastics but do so with very limited catalytic activity [1]. Several enzymes have been shown to degrade PET fibres but still suffer limitations in the range of plastic composition they are able to degrade [2, 3].

In RADICALZ, we have developed a novel methodology enabling rapid discovery of enzymes able to degrade PET fibres.

The workflow is made up of three main steps: 1. Screening of enzyme libraries and sorting of enzyme mutants into several separate activity levels, 2. Efficient DNA extraction and purification and 3. Next-generation sequencing. The screening technology is based on high-throughput encapsulation into water-in-oil emulsions which allowed us to screen up to 1 million enzyme mutants in a single experiment. We have applied this workflow to three PETase enzymes and obtained large datasets relating enzyme sequence to function. This has allowed us to find mutations which result in increased enzyme fitness and are continuing to characterise them thoroughly.

References

1. Yoshida, S., et al., *A bacterium that degrades and assimilates poly(ethylene terephthalate)*. *Science*, 2016. **351**(6278): p. 1196-9.
2. Tournier, V., et al., *An engineered PET depolymerase to break down and recycle plastic bottles*. *Nature*, 2020. **580**(7802): p. 216-219.
3. Sonnendecker, C., et al., *Low Carbon Footprint Recycling of Post-Consumer PET Plastic with a Metagenomic Polyester Hydrolase*. *ChemSusChem*, 2022. **15**(9): p. e202101062.

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